

LENGTH / EXTENT OF SMARANDACHE FACTOR PARTITIONS

(Amarnath Murthy ,S.E. (E &T), Well Logging Services,Oil And Natural Gas Corporation Ltd. ,Sabarmati, Ahmedbad, India- 380005.)

ABSTRACT: In [1] we define SMARANDACHE FACTOR PARTITION FUNCTION (SFP) , as follows:

Let $\alpha_1 , \alpha_2 , \alpha_3 , \dots \alpha_r$ be a set of r natural numbers and $p_1 , p_2 , p_3 , \dots p_r$ be arbitrarily chosen distinct primes then $F(\alpha_1 , \alpha_2 , \alpha_3 , \dots \alpha_r)$ called the Smarandache Factor Partition of $(\alpha_1 , \alpha_2 , \alpha_3 , \dots \alpha_r)$ is defined as the number of ways in which the number

$N = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} p_3^{\alpha_3} \dots p_r^{\alpha_r}$ could be expressed as the

product of its' divisors. For simplicity , we denote $F(\alpha_1 , \alpha_2 , \alpha_3 , \dots \alpha_r) = F' (N)$,where

$N = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} p_3^{\alpha_3} \dots p_r^{\alpha_r} \dots p_n^{\alpha_n}$

and p_r is the r^{th} prime. $p_1 = 2, p_2 = 3$ etc.

Also for the case

$$\alpha_1 = \alpha_2 = \alpha_3 = \dots = \alpha_r = \dots = \alpha_n = 1$$

we denote

$$F(\underset{\leftarrow n \text{ - ones}}{1, 1, 1, 1, 1, \dots}) = F(1\#n) \rightarrow$$

In the present note we define two interesting parameters the

length and **extent** of an **SFP** and study the interesting properties they exhibit for square free numbers.

DISCUSSION:

DEFINITION: Let $F'(N) = R$

LENGTH : If we denote each SFP of N , say like F_1, F_2, \dots, F_R arbitrarily and let F_k be the SFP representation of N as the product of its divisors as follows:

$F_k \text{ ---- } N = (h_1)(h_2)(h_3)(h_4) \dots (h_t)$, where each h_i ($1 < i < t$) is an entity in the SFP ' F_k ' of N . Then $T(F_k) = t$ is defined as the '**length**' of the factor partition F_k .

e.g. say $60 = 15 \times 2 \times 2$, is a factor partition F_k of 60. Then

$$T(F_k) = 3.$$

$T(F_k)$ can also be defined as one more than the number of product signs in the factor partition.

EXTENT : The extent of a number is defined as the sum of the lengths of all the SFPs.

Consider $F(1\#3)$

$$N = p_1 p_2 p_3 = 2 \times 3 \times 5 = 30.$$

SN	Factor Partition	length
1	30	1
2	15 X 2	2
3	10 X 3	2
4	6 X 5	2
5	5 X 3 X 2	3

$$\text{Extent}(30) = \sum \text{length} = 10$$

We observe that

$$F(1\#4) - F(1\#3) = 10. = \text{Extent} \{ F(1\#4) \}$$

Consider $F(1\#4)$

$$N = 2 \times 3 \times 5 \times 7 = 210$$

SN	Factor Partition	Length
1	210	1
2	105 X 2	2
3	70 X 3	2
4	42 X 5	2
5	35 X 6	2
6	35 X 3 X 2	3
7	30 X 7	2
8	21 X 10	2
9	21 X 5 X 2	3
10	15 X 14	2
11	15 X 7 X 2	3
12	14 X 5 X 2	3
13	10 X 7 X 3	3
14	7 X 6 X 5	3
15	7 X 5 X 3 X 2	4

$$\text{Extent}(210) = \sum \text{length} = 37$$

We observe that

$$F(1\#5) - F(1\#4) = 37. = \text{Extent} \{ F(1\#4) \}$$

Similarly it has been verified that

$$F(1\#6) - F(1\#5) = \text{Extent} \{ F(1\#5) \}$$

CONJECTURE (6.1)

$$F(1\#(n+1)) - F(1\#n) = \text{Extent} \{ F(1\#n) \}$$

CONJECTURE (6.2)

$$F(1\#(n+1)) = \sum_{r=0}^n \text{Extent} \{ F(1\#r) \}$$

Motivation for this conjecture:

If conjecture (1) is true then we would have

$$F(1\#2) - F(1\#1) = \text{Extent} \{ F(1\#1) \}$$

$$F(1\#3) - F(1\#2) = \text{Extent} \{ F(1\#2) \}$$

$$F(1\#4) - F(1\#3) = \text{Extent} \{ F(1\#3) \}$$

⋮
⋮
⋮

$$F(1\#(n+1)) - F(1\#n) = \text{Extent} \{ F(1\#n) \}$$

Summing up we would get

$$F(1\#(n+1)) - F(1\#1) = \sum_{r=1}^n \text{Extent} \{ F(1\#r) \}$$

$F(1\#1) = 1 = \text{Extent} \{ F(1\#0) \}$ can be taken, hence we get

$$F(1\#(n+1)) = \sum_{r=0}^n \text{Extent} \{ F(1\#r) \}$$

Another Interesting Observation:

Given below is the chart of r versus w where w is the number of

SFPs having same length r .

$$F(1\#0) = 1, \sum r \cdot w = 1$$

r	1
w	1

$$F(1\#1) = 1, \sum r \cdot w = 1$$

r	1
w	1

$$F(1\#2) = 2, \sum r \cdot w = 3$$

r	1	2
w	1	1

$$F(1\#3) = 5, \sum r \cdot w = 10$$

r	1	2	3
w	1	3	1

$$F(1\#4) = 15, \quad \sum r \cdot w = 37$$

r	1	2	3	4
w	1	7	6	1

$$F(1\#5) = 52, \quad \sum r \cdot w = 151$$

r	1	2	3	4	5
w	1	15	25	10	1

The interesting observation is the row of w is the same as the n^{th} row of the **SMARANDACHE STAR TRIANGLE**. (ref.: [4])

CONJECTURE (6.3)

$$w_r = a_{(n,r)} = (1/r!) \sum_{k=0}^r (-1)^{r-k} \cdot {}^r C_k \cdot k^n$$

where w_r is the number of SFPs of $F(1\#n)$ having length r .

Further Scope: One can study the length and contents of other cases (other than the square-free numbers.) explore for patterns if any.

REFERENCES:

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- [4] " The Florentine Smarandache " Special Collection, Archives of American Mathematics, Centre for American History, University of Texax at Austin, USA.